

Determination of Sulphur Functions with *o*-Diacetoxy Iodobenzoate

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Manuscript received 2 November 1976, revised 1 March 1977, accepted 27 April 1977

Procedures are evolved for the determination of some sulphur containing functional groups. *o*-Diacetoxy iodobenzoate is proposed and used as an analytical reagent for the determination of mercaptans, thioureas, organic sulphides, disulphides in dilute acetic acid medium and organic derivatives of dithiocarbonic acid at pH 7. The accuracy of the determination of mercaptans is 0.2%, of thioureas 0.5%, organic sulphides and disulphides 0.4%, and of organic derivatives of dithiocarbonic acid 0.5%. All the four methods are precise to 0.2-0.5%.

AMONG all compound of halogens, iodoso compounds are peculiar to iodine only. Similar compounds of other halogens either do not exist at all or are too unstable to be used as analytical reagents. The peculiarity of iodoso compounds lies in the fact that the iodine, even though in a positive oxidation state, must be linked to a carbon atom attached to a double bond. No stable compounds of positive iodine are known containing comparatively electro-positive saturated aliphatic radicals.

Hellerman et al¹ devised a method for determining cysteine with *o*-iodosobenzoate. But when this was applied to enzymes, inactivation was noticed. Finally, Hellerman opined that inactivation of enzymes could result from competitive inhibition by benzoate moiety rather than any effect of -SH groups. In the course of a systematic study on the determination of sulphhydryl compounds consideration was given to the behaviour of a series of iodoso compounds. Thus, *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate was synthesized and a stoichiometric relationship for the oxidation of mercaptans in dilute acetic acid medium was established.

The reaction is immediate and can be used for the direct titration of mercaptans. This aroused a great deal of interest with a view to find out its possible application in the field of other sulphur functions.

o-Diacetoxy iodobenzoate can also be employed for the quantitative oxidation of thioureas in 80-30% acetic acid medium; corresponding urea and sulphate ion are the reaction products.

where, R = alkyl or Aryl group.

Thiosemicarbazide reacts as follows :

Determination of organic sulphides and disulphides by the procedure of Siggia *et al*² yields reliable results. But with coloured sample and crude materials, the end point is indistinct since appearance of first permanent bromine coloration is taken as the end point. The results are vitiated by the presence of a large amount of mercaptans because bromine oxidation of mercaptans is somewhat non-stoichiometric. *o*-Diacetoxy iodobenzoate stoichiometrically oxidizes disulphides in dilute acetic acid; alpha-disulphone probably being the reaction products.

Samples were treated with an excess of *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate in 30-80% acetic acid medium. The residual oxidant was determined by adding a measured excess of mercaptoacetic acid (it reacts in a molar ratio of 2 : 1 with *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate) followed by a back titration with standard iodine.

The same procedure is applied to determine organic sulphides, which are oxidized to sulphoxides.

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As high as 3-fold excess of the oxidant does not cause high results. Mercaptans, if present, cause serious interference in the determination of sulphides and disulphides. They are to be determined separately and the results be corrected for. In the present procedure sulphide or disulphide samples containing mercaptans are determined by first evaluating the mercaptan by the procedure described before. An identical sample is then titrated with *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate to the first ascertained titre in the absence of any starch-iodide so as to convert mercaptan into the disulphide; the total sulphide and disulphide is finally estimated. The amount of disulphide produced by the oxidation of mercaptan is subtracted out of the total value to get sulphide or disulphide originally present.

A new oxidimetric procedure is evolved for determining organic derivatives of dithiocarbonic acid involving oxidation with *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate at pH 7 thereby converting them to corresponding dioxanthogens.

This procedure has also been applied to evaluate carbon disulphide involving conversion to xanthate with potassium ethoxide and determination of xanthate formed with *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate.

Xanthate formation according to the above equation is quantitative in the absence of water.

Experimental

Reagents and Samples

Preparation of *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoic acid :

A mixture of 70 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide and 305 ml of acetic anhydride was stirred for 4 hrs at 40°. *o*-Iodobenzoic acid 60.7 g, was then added to the solution which was stirred for further an hr and kept overnight. Some *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoic acid separated out and was filtered. The filtrate on concentration to a small volume under reduced pressure (70 mm) yielded a second crop. The combined needle shaped crystals were washed with ether and dried (over NaOH) in a vacuum desiccator, yield 63.0 g. m.p. 206°.

o-Diacetoxy iodobenzoate solution (0.05*N*) was prepared by addition to the solid sample of the reagent of a slight excess of 1*N* potassium hydroxide solution and finally diluting upto the mark. It was standardized iodimetrically. A 0.01*N* solution was made by diluting the concentrated reagent with water.

o-Diacetoxy iodobenzoate solution (0.05*M*) was

prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of sample in glacial acetic acid and was standardized iodimetrically.

Phosphate buffer (pH 7) was prepared by dissolving 117.7 g of K_2HPO_4 and 44.1 g of KH_2PO_4 in 1 litre of water.

Most of the mercaptans, substituted thioureas and all derivatives of dithiocarbonic acid were prepared and purified by the authors.

A C.P. grade carbon disulphide was used.

Procedure for determining mercaptans :

A Sample containing 0.1-0.5 meq of mercaptan was weighed into a 150-ml Erl enmeyer flask containing 50 ml of distilled water. Sample, if insoluble in water, was dissolved in 10-15 ml of 99% acetic acid and at the time of titration sufficient water was added to bring acid concentration roughly 40-30% v/v. Less water may be used if sample comes out badly (at high acetic acid concentrations, reaction is slow and the end point is not of the sharpest type). About 50 mg of potassium iodide and 1 ml of 1% starch solution were added and the solution titrated with 0.01*N* *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate when upto 0.2 meq of mercaptan was present and 0.05*N* reagent solution was used for larger sample size. The end point is shown by a blue colour of starch-iodine.

Procedure for determining thioureas :

An aliquot of the sample, dissolved in water or 99% acetic acid, containing 0.01-0.1 meq of thiourea, was pipetted into a 250-ml Erl enmeyer flask. Acetic acid solution of 0.05*M* *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate was added, about 50% in excess. Prior to the addition of *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate calculated volumes of water were added to keep acid concentration between 80-30% v/v. Flask was kept aside for at least 30 mins. Thereafter, a measured excess of 0.05*M* solution of mercaptoacetic acid and 3 ml of 1*M* sulphuric acid were added and after 30 sec the residual amount of mercaptoacetic acid was titrated with 0.04*N* solution of iodine to a starch-iodine blue colour. Concurrently, a blank determination was also carried out.

Procedure for determining sulphides and disulphides:

A sample containing 0.1-0.5 mmole of sulphide or 0.02-0.08 mmole of disulphide was weighed into a 250-ml Erl enmeyer flask and dissolved in 15-20 ml of 99% acetic acid. A 0.05*M* solution of *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate was added about 50% in excess along with calculated volumes of distilled water so as to adjust acid concentration between 30-80%, v/v (reactions are slow in anhydrous acetic acid and catalysed moderately by water. Less water was used when the sample precipitates out). Flask was left for at least 20 mins (40 minutes in the case of methi-

onine and overnight when cystine was being determined) after which a measured excess of 0.05M solution of mercaptoacetic acid and 3 ml of 1M sulphuric acid was added and the contents swirled. The residual amount of mercaptoacetic acid was back titrated with 0.05N iodine solution using starch as indicator.

A blank determination was also run separately.

Procedure for determining organic derivatives of dithiocarbonic acid :

A sample containing 0.1-1.0 meq of sodium or potassium salt of dithiocarbonic acid was weighed into a 150-ml Erl enmeyer flask and dissolved in 10 ml of water. After which 5 ml of phosphate buffer, and 10 ml of suitably diluted aqueous solution of *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate was added so that it was about 50% in excess. The contents were swirled for 30 sec and then a measured excess of 0.05M solution of mercaptoacetic acid and 3 ml of sulphuric acid were added. After swirling for 30 sec the residual mercaptoacetic acid was titrated with 0.04N iodine solution to a starch-iodine blue colour.

A blank determination was also carried out in the same way.

Procedure for determining carbon disulphide :

A sample containing 0.1-1.0 mmole of carbon disulphide was weighed in a small sealed glass bulb

and placed beneath a mixture of 0.5-2.0 ml of freshly prepared 10% potassium ethoxide and 5 ml of absolute ethanol contained in a 150 ml Erl enmeyer flask. A sharp rap against the side of the flask was sufficient to break the bulb and to release the sample. The contents were swirled for 2 mins and the flask was cooled in an ice bath. Thereafter 20 ml of water and 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added and the base content was titrated with 1M acetic acid until the solution was just acid to the indicator. A suitable volume of phosphate buffer (pH 7) and 10 ml of *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate solution were added. The excess of the oxidant was determined after 30 secs using the method described before.

A blank determination was also carried out.

Results and Discussions

Results for the determination of several mercaptans Table 1 show that the method is sufficiently accurate. Cysteine, 3-mercaptopropionic, *o*-mercaptobenzoic and mercaptosuccinic acids are over-oxidized and the present method is not recommended for them. Results for determining thioureas Table 2 showed excellent agreement with the amount of sample taken especially when dilute solutions were used. Diphenylthiourea does not react stoichiometrically. Quantitative results for the analysis of pure as well as crude samples of sulphide

TABLE—1 DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS WITH *o*-DIACETOXY IODOBENZOATE

Mercaptan titrated	Purity, %	
	Present Method ^a	Comparison method
Ethanethiol	100.1	99.8
Glutathione	98.0	98.1
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzenethiol	96.2	96.1
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	96.4	96.6
<i>p</i> -Toluenethiol	98.5	98.4
2-Diethylaminoethanethiol HCl	98.1	98.2
1-Propanethiol	94.8	94.5
Toluene- α -thiol	98.5	98.2
Mercaptoacetic acid	80.0	80.3
Thiobenzoic acid	95.3	95.0
2-Mercaptobenzothiazole	98.0	97.8
1-Butanethiol	90.3	90.6
2-Mercaptoethanol	99.5	99.3
Allylthiol	93.4	93.2
<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene- α -thiol	98.4	98.7
2-Butanethiol	97.2	97.4
2-Mercaptoethylammonium chloride	97.4	97.5
1-Pentanethiol	88.2	88.4
Methyl 3-mercaptopropionate	96.2	96.0
Benzenethiol	98.7	99.0
2 Naphthalenethiol	99.3	99.1
Toluenethiol (mixed isomers)	93.2	93.0
<i>m</i> -Mercaptobenzoic acid	99.5	99.7
<i>m</i> -Chlorothiophenol	98.8	99.0
<i>o</i> -Toluenethiol	98.1	98.3
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzenethiol	99.6	99.8
Glycerol-1 thiol	79.2	79.0
Cyclohexanethiol	95.3	95.7
		Iodimetry ³
		Iodimetry ⁴
		Pb ⁴⁺ titration ⁵
		ICl titration ⁶
		Co ³⁺ titration ⁷
		Chloramine T ⁸
		Cu ²⁺ titration ⁹
		Acetylation ¹⁰
		Periodate titration ¹¹
		Alkalimetry ¹²
		NBS titration ¹³
		PIA titration ¹⁴
		Cu ²⁺ titration ¹⁵
		Acetylation ¹⁰
		Iodimetry ³
		NBB titration ¹⁶
		OIB titration ¹⁷
		Hg ²⁺ titration ¹⁸
		Iodimetry ³
		Nitric titration ¹⁹
		Cu ²⁺ titration ²⁰
		Alkalimetry ¹²
		Iodimetry ³
		PIA titration ¹⁴
		Iodimetry ³
		Pb ⁴⁺ titration ⁵
		Ferricyanide reaction ²¹
		Cu ²⁺ titration ²⁰

a, Mean of 10 determinations ; relative standard deviation in the range 0.1-0.3%.

TABLE—2 DETERMINATION OF THIOUREAS WITH *o*-DIACETOXY IODOBENZOATE

Sample	Purity, %		Comparison method
	Present Method ^a		
Thiourea	99.7	99.9	Hypiodite ²²
Thiosemicarbazide	99.3	99.6	Nitrite titration ²³
Phenylthiourea	99.7	100.1	Bromimetry ²⁴
<i>o</i> -Tolylthiourea	96.8	97.2	Chloramine-T ²⁵
<i>p</i> -Tolylthiourea	98.2	98.5	Iodine monochloride ²⁶
Allylthiourea	96.6	96.1	Sulphur analysis
<i>p</i> -Bromophenylthiourea	95.6	96.0	Iodine monochloride ²⁶
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenylthiourea	98.2	97.9	Bromimetry ²⁴
<i>p</i> -Anisylthiourea	99.9	100.4	Iodine trichloride ²⁷
<i>m</i> -Anisylthiourea	97.0	97.4	Iodine monochloride ²⁶
<i>n</i> -Butylthiourea	98.7	99.0	Cerimetry ²⁸
<i>n</i> -Amylthiourea	99.6	99.2	Cerimetry ²⁸
<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenylthiourea	98.4	98.2	Chloramine-T ²⁵
<i>p</i> -Tolylthiourea	98.0	97.4	Pb ⁴⁺ titration ²⁹
Methylthiourea	98.2	98.1	Nonaqueous cerimetry ³⁰

a Average of 10 determinations ; relative standard deviation in the range 0.2-0.5%

and disulphide are given in Tables 3-5. In Table 6, results are given for the determination of disulphides formed by titration of mercaptan solution with

TABLE—3 DETERMINATION OF SULPHIDE WITH *o*-DIACETOXY IODOBENZOATE

Sample	Purity, %		Comparison method
	Present Method		
Dibenzylsulphide	98.9	99.3	Total sulphur analysis
Methyl <i>n</i> -propylsulphide	95.4	96.1	Bromimetry ³
Methionine	99.5	100.1	PIA titration ³¹
Di <i>n</i> -butylsulphide	99.8	99.5	Bromimetry ²

TABLE—4 DETERMINATION OF DISULPHIDES WITH *o*-DIACETOXY IODOBENZOATE

Sample	Purity, %	
	Present Method	Bromimetry ²
Cystine	99.0	99.3
Di <i>n</i> -butyldisulphide	97.3	96.9
Di <i>n</i> -benzyldisulphide	99.7	100.2
Di <i>n</i> -pentyldisulphide	98.4	98.1
Di <i>n</i> -propyldisulphide	94.7	94.6
Diphenyldisulphide	95.3	95.7

o-diacetoxy iodobenzoate. As a check, sulphides and disulphides were determined by the method of Siggia³ and by total sulphur analysis (Tables 3 & 4).

TABLE—5 DETERMINATION OF CRUDE SAMPLES

Sample	Purity, %	
	Present Method	Total sulphur analysis
Dibenzylsulphide	87.6	88.3
Di <i>n</i> -butylsulphide	79.7	81.1
Dibenzylsulphide	84.3	84.4

Purity of crude samples were determined by total sulphur analysis (Table 5). Table 7 summarizes the results for the determination of organic derivatives of dithiocarbonic acid and carbon disulphide. The time allowed for complete reaction in this case should not be increased as dixanthogens also get

TABLE—6 DETERMINATION OF DISULPHIDES FORMED IN COMPLETELY TITRATED MERCAPTAN SOLUTION

	mole		
	RSH Titrated	RSSR Formed	RSSR Recovery ³ (%)
Mercaptoacetic acid	0.582	0.289	99.3
1-Butanethiol	0.759	0.380	100.3
1-Pentanethiol	0.286	0.142	99.8
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	1.163	0.578	99.2
Benzenethiol	1.029	0.516	100.3
Toluene- α -thiol	0.874	0.431	98.5

a % recovery takes into account theoretically calculated value.

TABLE—7 DETERMINATION OF CARBON-DISULPHIDE AND ORGANIC DERIVATIVES OF DITHIOCARBONIC ACID BY *o*-DIACETOXY IODOBENZOATE

Sample	Purity, %		
	Present Method ²	Iodine titration ^{3a-3d}	Sulphur Analysis
K Methylxanthate	96.5	96.9	97.6
Na Ethylxanthate	89.4	90.1	89.8
K <i>n</i> -Propylxanthate	99.6	99.8	99.9
K <i>n</i> -Butylxanthate	94.1	93.9	94.5
K <i>iso</i> -Propylxanthate	78.6	79.1	78.8
K <i>iso</i> -Butylxanthate	92.3	92.9	92.6
K Amylxanthate	96.8	97.1	97.5
K <i>iso</i> -Amylxanthate	94.7	94.4	95.0
K Allylxanthate	93.9	94.3	95.3
K Cyclohexylxanthate	75.7	76.2	76.1
K <i>sec</i> -Butylxanthate	98.9	99.1	99.6
Carbon disulphide	95.2	94.8	—

a Average of 10 determinations ; relative standard deviation in the range 0.3-0.5%.

oxidized slowly by an excess of *o*-diacetoxy iodobenzoate. In Table 8, results are given for the determination of mercaptans and derivatives of dithiocarbonic acid in the presence of foreign substances. The substances chosen to study the effect, include compounds that interfere in other methods and compounds that contain other sulphur functions. In the determination of thioureas large amounts of glycine,

TABLE—8 DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS, AND XANTHATES IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN SUBSTANCES

Sample determined	Substance added	Molar ratio, added subs/sample	Recovery, (%)
Mercaptopropionic acid	Potassium cyanide	83 : 1	100.7
	Dimethylsulphoxide	314 : 1	100.0
	Diethylsulphide	14 : 1	100.0
K <i>n</i> -Butylxanthate	Acrylonitrile	60 : 1	99.7
	Diacetonealcohol	7 : 1	100.2
	Dimethylsulphoxide	38 : 1	99.0
	Acetone	9 : 1	99.9
2-Mercaptoethanol	Thiophene	10 : 1	100.5
	Dibenzylsulphide	70 : 1	100.0
	Alanine	69 : 1	100.1
K Allylxanthate	Formic acid	90 : 1	100.5
	Carbon disulphide	58 : 1	101.2
	Cystine	27 : 1	100.1
	Glycine	34 : 1	100.0
	Alanine	44 : 1	100.0
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	Thiophene	19 : 1	101.8
	Dextrose	170 : 1	100.2
	Carbon disulphide	105 : 1	100.2
	Methylacrylate	10 : 1	101.0
	Acrylonitrile	94 : 1	99.7

a Average of 4 determinations ; % recovery takes into account 'previously determined purity of sample (Table 3).

alanine, formic acid, dextrose and urea do not interfere but organic sulphides and disulphides interfere. In the determination of sulphides and disulphides, alanine, glycine, dextrose, fumaric, cinnamic and formic acids can be tolerated.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Dr. B. P. Sinha for encouragement, to University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for awarding a post-doctoral fellowship to A. S. and to C. S. I. R. for a senior fellowship to J. A.

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